

The Influence of Social Media Marketing on Purchase Intention with the Brand Image and Brand Trust as the Mediating Variables on Hydraulic Excavator Spare Parts in Indonesia

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Abstract:- This research aims to examine the influence of Social Media Marketing on Purchase Intention with Brand Image and Brand Trust as the Mediation Variables on Hydraulic Excavator spare parts products in Indonesia. This research uses a causal research method. The research population is the consumers of hydraulic pump spare parts for Hydraulic Excavators in Indonesia. The samples are set using a non-probability technique, involving 178 respondents as the consumers of Hydraulic Excavator spare parts at PT. MPU. The data are analyzed using SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) SmartPLS version 3.0. The results show that: (1) Social Media Marketing has a positive and significant influence on Purchase Intention; (2) Social Media Marketing has a positive and significant influence on Brand Image; (3) Social Media Marketing has a positive and significant influence on Brand Trust; (4) Brand Image has a positive and significant influence on Purchase Intention; (5) Brand Trust has a positive and significant influence on Purchase Intention; (6) Brand Image mediates the relationship between Social Media Marketing and Purchase Intention, and; (7) Brand Trust mediates the relationship between Social Media Marketing and Purchase Intention.

Keywords:- Social Media Marketing, Brand Image, Brand Trust, Purchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

As a developing country, since 2018 Indonesia has been included as one of the most progressive countries in the construction and infrastructure sectors. The increasing number of investments in both sectors has greatly affected the need for reliable and high-quality resources. One of the most required resources is the availability of heavy equipment to conduct construction, development, and building activities. Heavy equipment refers to vehicles or tools specifically designed to carry out heavy tasks and assist construction programs which are often used for earthwork operations [1]. Based on the data taken from dataindustri.com [2], from 2009 to 2020 there have been four main brands of heavy equipment that dominate the Indonesian market, namely Komatsu, Caterpillar, Hitachi, and Kobelco.

One of the most commonly found heavy equipment in construction projects is the excavator. It uses a diesel engine that converts mechanical into motion energy through pump pressure. This pump is known as a hydraulic pump. Because the hydraulic pump is a source for the movement of an excavator, it is also often known as the Hydraulic Excavator. The vital role of the hydraulic pump makes PT. Multindo Persada Utama (PT. MPU) and many other companies are interested in working on the business of selling hydraulic pumps, both in intact and decomposed forms (spare parts). There are many brands of hydraulic pump spare parts, one of which is the “HT TECH” which is sold by PT. MPU.

The sales data of PT. MPU from 2017-2020 shows that the highest sales value was in 2017, but the next periods have never exceeded the 2017 sales rate. If the sales growth data of PT. MPU compared to three other companies operating in the same segment, what is interesting is the sales growth of PT. MPU looks volatile and contradicts the others. Nugraha et al. [3] stated that sales growth is strongly connected to the consumers’ purchasing decisions. In their research on Komatsu Excavator purchasing decisions, Prabowo, Brahmasari & Suryani [4] concluded that one of the variables that have a positive and significant impact on the consumers’ purchasing decisions is purchase intention.

Kosasih [5] explained some problems related to the purchase intention of aftermarket spare parts products in Indonesia. The first aspect is the number of counterfeit spare parts, both genuine and aftermarket, which circulate in the market. The second one is that there are many brands of aftermarket spare parts in circulation, which makes the consumers get confused to choosing which brands that suit their needs. The third aspect is related to the consumers’ protection, where there have been no mandatory provisions for the Indonesian National Standard (SNI) and the obligation to include product description labels in the Indonesian language, the countries where the products come from, as well as the name of the importers for heavy equipment spare parts.

The reviews of some previous research journals have found seven variables that significantly affect purchase intention. A pre-survey was conducted to select three out of

the seven variables, taking into account the limited time of the research. The results showed three variables with the largest percentage that will be used in this research, namely: social media marketing, brand image, and brand trust.

There have been some studies conducted to examine the relationship among these three variables on purchase intention. Yadav & Rahman [6], Sanny et al. [7], and Manzoor et al. [8] concluded that social media marketing has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention. However, they emphasized the need for further research to examine this effect because different results could be obtained if the research was conducted in different industrial categories. In other studies, Prabowo, Brahmasari & Suryani [4], Suhud & Wilson [9], and Sanny et al. [7] found that brand image has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention. However, Harsono et al. [10], Razy & Lazevardi [11] stated that brand image has no significant effect on purchase intention. Sanny et al. [7] and Cuong [12] explained that brand trust has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention. However, Harsono et al. [10], Hansopaheluwakan, Oey & Setiawan [13] declared that brand trust has no significant effect on purchase intention. From the descriptions above, there are still gaps in contradictory findings related to the relationship among these variables that affect purchase intention. Besides, it has also been found the need to conduct further studies to generalize the previous findings. Therefore, the author is interested to conduct this research to further investigate the relationship among these variables.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Social Media Marketing

Universal Maccann International defines social media as online-based applications, platforms, and media that allow their users to interact, collaborate, and share any content [14]. Due to the rapid growth of social media users, social media has been commonly used in various marketing activities of many companies and organizations. This is why there is a term "social media marketing" [15]. Alhadid & Alhadeed (2017) argued that there is no doubt that social media marketing has become a trending marketing activity. It is because it has a very wide reach, ease of access, and lower costs [14]. Manzoor et al. [8] added that if we want our business ideas to be known by millions of people in a quite shorter time with minimal costs, the best choice is having social media for marketing our products or services.

B. Brand Image

Keller (2013) in Prabowo, Brahmasari & Suryani [4] described the brand image as an association about a brand that is embedded in the consumers' minds. Soltani, et al. [16] defined brand image as consumers' awareness of a brand, which is reflected by the brand association on their minds. Hien, et al. [17] added that the associations about a brand may come from the customers' experience, gathered information, or the impacts of those associations on their minds. In other words, the brand image focuses more on what the consumers think about the brand, and the emotions the brand evokes when they are thinking about it.

C. Brand Trust

Chinamona [18] defined brand trust as the consumers' trust in a particular brand that may satisfy their desires so that when they have strong trust in the brand, a close relationship between them and the brand can be built. Sanny, et al. [7] explained brand trust as the consumers' desire to rely on a brand with all the risks that may emerge later. Positive brand trust can increase the likelihood that the consumers will choose certain products. Based on these reasons, the companies have conducted a study involving consumers' perspectives on their brands to instill it into their minds which aims to form a positive brand image and brand trust by engaging in all communication channels [15].

D. Purchase Intention

Kim & Ko [14] explained purchase intention as the consumers' interest to make purchases in the future. According to Balakrishnan et al. [19], the interest in purchasing a product or service is set by how the customers' perception of the product or service. Lim et al. [20] defined purchase intention as the consumers' behavior that occurs when they are stimulated by external factors and make a purchase decision process based on their characteristics. In other words, according to Cuong [12], purchase intention is defined as an interest to buy a product in the future, after getting the desired information about it. Interest means that the person does not have or buys a product but already has the desire to buy it.

E. Conceptual Framework

This study adopts the conceptual framework by Sanny et al. [7] and Moslehpour et al. [21] by adding an indirect relationship mediating effect test. Based on the theory formulated from previous research journals, a conceptual framework can be drawn in the following Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

Based on Figure 1, seven hypotheses have been successfully formulated:

- H1: There is a positive and significant relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention.
- H2: There is a positive and significant relationship between social media marketing and brand image.
- H3: There is a positive and significant relationship between social media marketing and brand trust.
- H4: There is a positive and significant relationship between brand image and purchase intention.

- H5: There is a positive and significant relationship between brand trust and purchase intention.
 H6: Brand image mediates the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention.
 H7: Brand trust mediates the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research uses a causal research method. The population is the consumers who use hydraulic pump spare parts for hydraulic excavators in Indonesia. The research sample is taken from the consumers who are direct users of hydraulic pump spare parts for hydraulic excavators who have not and will make purchases at PT. MPU. The sampling method uses a non-probability technique with convenience sampling. The primary research data are obtained through a questionnaire distributed online to 178 respondents. The secondary data are gathered using literature reviews on some textbooks and journals. The primary data are then analyzed using SEM analysis with SmartPLS software version 3.0

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Respondents' Descriptions

The following are the characteristics of the 178 respondents who participate in this research. 89.89% respondents of the

respondents are male, and the rest are female. Based on education level, 49.44% of respondents have a bachelor's degree, 24.16% have a diploma degree, and the rest have other educational degrees. Based on age, most of the respondents are among 31-40 years old (52.25%), 41-50 years old (20.80%), and the rest are in other age ranges. Based on the place they are living, 57.88% of the respondents are currently living in Java and its surrounding areas, 14.04% are living in Sumatra and Kalimantan islands, 12.36% are living in Sulawesi Island and its surrounding areas, and the rest are living in other regions in Indonesia.

B. Validity Test

The validity test consists of convergent validity and discriminant validity tests. The PLS model is set to meet the convergent validity requirements if the loading factor value is higher than 0.7. It can also be seen from the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value, where the PLS model is declared to fulfill convergent validity if the AVE value of each construct is higher than 0.5. From TABLE I, it can be seen that the loading factor value of all indicators is higher than 0.7 and the AVE value of all constructs is also higher than 0.5. Therefore, it can be concluded that all indicators in each construct have met the required convergent validity criteria.

TABLE I. LOADING FACTOR AND AVE VALUES

No	Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	AVE	Note
1	<i>Social Media Marketing</i>	X1.1	0,802	0,660	Valid
		X1.2	0,804		Valid
		X1.3	0,815		Valid
		X1.4	0,833		Valid
		X1.5	0,836		Valid
		X1.6	0,788		Valid
		X1.7	0,828		Valid
		X1.8	0,809		Valid
		X1.9	0,799		Valid
		X1.10	0,806		Valid
2	<i>Purchase Intention</i>	Y1.1	0,792	0,664	Valid
		Y1.2	0,780		Valid
		Y1.3	0,800		Valid
		Y1.4	0,756		Valid
		Y1.5	0,871		Valid
		Y1.6	0,882		Valid
3	<i>Brand Image</i>	Z1.1	0,841	0,690	Valid
		Z1.2	0,821		Valid
		Z1.3	0,838		Valid
		Z1.4	0,840		Valid
		Z1.5	0,798		Valid
		Z1.6	0,844		Valid
4	<i>Brand Trust</i>	Z2.1	0,865	0,709	Valid
		Z2.2	0,832		Valid
		Z2.3	0,859		Valid
		Z2.4	0,818		Valid
		Z2.5	0,793		Valid
		Z2.6	0,882		Valid

The discriminant validity test refers to the Fornall Larcker Criterion. The model has good discriminant validity if the AVE square value of each exogenous construct (the value on the diagonal) exceeds the correlation between the construct and others (the value below the diagonal). The results of the Fornall Larcker Criterion test can be seen in TABLE II.

TABLE II. FORNALL LARSKER CRITERION

	Brand Image	Brand Trust	Purchase Intention	Social Media Marketing
Brand Image	0,830			
Brand Trust	0,824	0,842		
Purchase Intention	0,783	0,773	0,815	
Social Media Marketing	0,716	0,716	0,687	0,812

From TABLE II, it can be seen that all constructs have the square root value of AVE higher than the correlation value with other latent constructs. Therefore, it can be concluded that the model has met the discriminant validity requirements.

C. Reliability Test

The reliability test can be seen from the Cronbach's Alpha and the Composite Reliability values of each construct. The Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values should be higher than 0.7. The results ini TABLE III shows that all constructs have Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values higher than 0.7, so it means that all constructs have met the required reliability. It means that all constructs have met the required reliability, or it can be stated that the questionnaire is trusted and reliable.

TABLE III. RELIABILITY TEST

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Brand Image	0,910	0,930
Brand Trust	0,918	0,936
Purchase Intention	0,898	0,922
Social Media Marketing	0,943	0,951

D. R-square (R²) Value

The R² value can be seen in TABLE IV below.

TABLE IV. R-SQUARE VALUE

	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Purchase Intention	0,691	0,685

The R-square value shows the simultaneous effect of social media marketing, brand image, and brand trust on purchase intention. From TABLE IV, it can be seen that the R-Square value is 0.691 with an R-Square Adjusted value of 0.685. This can be interpreted as the effect of social media marketing variables, brand image, and brand trust simultaneously on purchase intention of 69.10%, while the rest is influenced by other variables not included in this research.

E. The goodness of Fit Model Test

The PLS fit model can be seen from the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) value. The PLS model is declared to have met the criteria for the goodness of fit model if the SRMR value is lower than 0.10, and the model is declared perfectly fit if the SRMR value is lower than 0.08.

TABLE V. GOODNESS OF FIT MODEL

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0,056	0,090

TABLE V shows that the SRMR value of 0.056 is lower than 0.10, even lower than 0.08. Therefore, it can be concluded that the PLS model is declared perfectly fit, so it is feasible to be used in this research.

F. Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis testing is started from the path coefficient value, T statistic value, and P-value through the bootstrapping procedure. If the path coefficient is positive, P-value < 0.05, and T statistic value > 1.96, then the hypothesis is accepted. From the results of bootstrapping in the image, all paths are significant with T statistic > 1.96. The complete hypotheses testing results can be seen in Figure 2 and Table VI.

Fig. 2. Research Model Result

TABLE VI. HYPOTESIS TESTING RESULTS

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample Mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T Statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P Values</i>	<i>Note</i>
<i>SMM -> PI</i>	0,175	0,172	0,060	2,896	0,004	Accepted
<i>SMM -> BI</i>	0,716	0,710	0,049	14,610	0,000	Accepted
<i>SMM -> BT</i>	0,716	0,710	0,049	14,604	0,000	Accepted
<i>BI -> PI</i>	0,386	0,388	0,078	4,979	0,000	Accepted
<i>BT -> PI</i>	0,329	0,330	0,092	3,569	0,000	Accepted
<i>SMM -> BI -> PI</i>	0,276	0,276	0,059	4,683	0,000	Accepted
<i>SMM-> BT -> PI</i>	0,236	0,235	0,069	3,407	0,001	Accepted

Information :

-SMM : Social Media Marketing

-PI : Purchase Intention

-BI : Brand Image

-BT : Brand Trust

The influence of social media marketing on purchase intention has a positive path coefficient (+0.175), a P-Value of 0.004 (<0.05), and a T-statistic of 2.896 (>1.96). Therefore, it can be concluded that H1 is accepted. There is a positive and significant influence of social media marketing on purchase intention. The results of this research are in line with Yadav & Rahman [6], Alfeel & Ansari [22], and Sanny et al. [7].

The effect of social media marketing on the brand image has a positive path coefficient (+0.716), P-Value 0.000 (<0.05), and a T-statistic of 14.610 (>1.96). It can be concluded that H2 is accepted, and there is a positive and significant influence of social media marketing on brand image. The result is similar to Bilgin [15], Sanny et al. [7], Moslehpour et al. [21].

The effect of social media marketing on brand trust has a positive path coefficient (+0.716), P-Value 0.000 (<0.05), and a T-statistic of 14.604 (>1.96). It can be concluded that H3 is accepted, and there is a positive and significant influence of social media marketing on brand image. The result is the same with Tümer et al. [23] and Sanny, et al. [7].

The effect of brand image on purchase intention has a positive path coefficient (+0.386), a P-Value of 0.000 (<0.05), and a T-statistic of 4.979 (>1.96). Therefore, it can be concluded that H4 is accepted, and there is a positive and significant relationship between brand image and purchase intention. The result is in line with Dehganı & Tumer [24], Prabowo, Brahmasari & Suryani [4] and Sanny et al. [7]. However, in another study, Razy & Lazevardi [11] and Harsono et al. [10] explained the opposite findings. This is most likely due to the different products and industries as the research objects, so it is not possible if there are different findings obtained.

The effect of brand trust on purchase intention has a positive path coefficient (+0.392), a P-Value of 0.000 (<0.05), and a T statistic of 3.569 (>1.96). Therefore, it can be concluded that H5 is accepted, and there is a positive and significant influence of brand trust on purchase intention. This is in line with Tümer et. al [23] and Cuong [12]. However, the

result contradicts the findings obtained by Hansopaheluwakan, Oey & Setiawan [13] and Harsono et al. [10]. The different result is most likely caused by the different products and industries that become research objects so that it is normal if there are different findings.

The mediating effect of brand image has a positive path coefficient (+0.276), P-Value 0.000 (<0.05), and a T-statistic of 4.683 (>1.96). Therefore, it can be concluded that H6 is accepted, and brand image mediates the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention. Little et al. (2010) in Budhiasa [25] divided the mediation model into four conditions, namely: full mediation, partial mediation, inconsistent mediation, and non-mediation. From the hypothesis 1 and 5 which have been examined previously, the coefficient value of the direct relationship of social media marketing to purchase intention is 0.175; the coefficient value of social media marketing to the brand image is 0.716 (> 0.175), and the coefficient value of the brand image to purchase intention is 0.386 (> 0.175). Such a finding fulfills a model called partial mediation.

The mediating effect of brand trust has a positive path coefficient (+0.236), P-Value 0.000 (<0.05), and a T-statistic of 3.407 (>1.96). It means that H7 is accepted, and brand trust mediates the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention. Based on the mediation conditions proposed by Little et al. (2010) in Budhiasa [25], the brand trust mediating relationship also meets the partial mediation model.

This research raises some managerial implications. The important role of social media marketing must be utilized optimally by the company. Also, the number of social media users has been growing rapidly from time to time. The companies must be able to package social media content in exciting and interesting ways to create deeper impressions that aim to win the competitions. Besides, the marketing strategies deployed must also be able to build a positive brand image and brand trust for the consumers. Either through direct relationships or mediation, brand trust and brand image can strengthen purchase intention. Another crucial aspect is that the companies must have more comprehensive marketing strategies because purchase intention is not only influenced by these three research variables.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusions

Based on the results of hypothesis testing and discussions that have been stated previously, several conclusions can be drawn: (1) social media marketing has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention; the higher the positive responses to a brand's social media marketing activities, the higher the consumers' purchase intention, and vice versa; (2) social media marketing has a positive and significant influence on the brand image; the higher the positive responses to the social media marketing activities, the better the brand image for the consumers, and vice versa; (3) social media marketing has a positive and significant influence on brand trust; the higher the positive responses to the social media marketing activities, the better the brand trust according to the consumers, and vice versa; (4) brand image has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention. It means that the better the brand image, the higher the consumers' purchase intention for a brand, and vice versa; (5) brand trust has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention; the higher the brand trust from the consumers, the higher the consumers' purchase intention for a brand, and vice versa; (6) brand image mediates the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention, and; (7) brand trust mediates the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention.

B. Suggestions

Some practical suggestions can be given to PT. MPU related to these research findings: (1) in managing social media accounts, the company should pay more attention to improving the facilitation of two-way interactions among its followers; (2) the company must intensify and educate its customers about the advantages of the HT TECH brand compared to other competitors; (3) the company must be able to improve the quality of services constantly from time to time; (4) the company must improve the current marketing strategies because the HT TECH brand has not yet become the main choice for the consumers in the market. The company can implement more comprehensive marketing strategies in growing its customers base. It is because based on the results of the research, it turns out that purchase intention is influenced by more than one variable.

Based on the research limitations, some suggestions can be given for further research. This research has some limitations because it only uses social media marketing, brand image, and brand trust variables to identify their influences on purchase intention. Further research should add other variables such as brand loyalty, brand awareness, and testing the mediating effect on purchase intention. Besides, this research has a limited number of respondents, sampling techniques, and only examines direct users of hydraulic excavator spare parts. Further research should add more respondents by paying attention to the techniques and representativeness of the sample. The next researchers should also focus on several companies that are not only oriented to the direct users to better validate the research findings. This research does not take into account changes in consumers' behavior due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Future research can be conducted by

adding the influence of the consumers' behavior that may change dynamically.

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